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Research Article

**A RESEARCH TO JUDGE AN ABNORMAL GLUCOSE
TOLERANCE REGULARITY IN B-THALASSEMIA MAJOR
CHILDREN TREATED WITH REGULAR BLOOD
TRANSFUSION**¹Mishal Saleem, ²Muhammad Ibrahim, ²Shehroz Rehman
¹UHS, Lahore, ²Islamabad Medical and Dental College**Abstract**

Objective: The purpose of the research was to judge the regularity of abnormal glucose tolerance in children with β thalassemia major over frequent blood transfusion.

Material and methods: Researcher performed the research at Mayo Hospital, Lahore from April to October 2017. The researcher enrolled one hundred and sixty-one patients of β thalassemia major with three to twenty years of age for research.

Results: The number of patients having age between three to ten years in eighty-six (53.24%) along with seventy-five (46.58%) patients, having age between eleven to twenty years with an average age of (10.55 + 4.90) years. Among one hundred and sixty-one enrolled patients, the number of male and female was ninety-seven (60.25%) and sixty-four (39.75%) patients respectively as well as regularity of vitiated glucose tolerance discovered in seventeen (10.56%) patients

Conclusion: Researcher finalized that the regularity of abnormal glucose tolerance in children with β thalassemia major over frequent blood transfusion is too high, whereas several additional research on the same topic is mandatory for verification of our results.

Keywords: Impaired Glucose Tolerance (IGT), β -Thalassemia Major, Red Blood Cell (RBC), OGTT (Oral Glucose Tolerance Test) and Haemoglobin (Hb).

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INTRODUCTION:

The β thalassemia major is autosome bashful situation that influences the volume of Hb molecules inside to red blood cells. The β thalassemia major emerges due to a permutation in beta-globin genes on chromosomes [1]. The most frequent and common disease in Pakistan, Mediterranean zones, India as well as in middle east states is beta thalassemia major [2]. Approximately (1.5%) of the peoples of the world are influenced by β thalassemia major [3]. Six to nineteen percent is a percentage of β thalassemia major in Greece, β thalassemia major percentage in Cyprus is fifteen to seventeen percent, Iran four to five percent, Saudi Arabia one to two percent and Pakistan one to eight percent [4 – 6]. Four to six children having β thalassemia major required frequent lifelong RBC transfusion for their protection. By these patients, a lot of the issues engaged are certainly the difficulties of transfusion instead of disease difficulties itself and overburden iron is counted as one of them. Overburden iron may advance to endocrinal difficulties progression particularly IGT (Impaired glucose tolerance). The periodicity of IGT (Impaired glucose tolerance) alters from (7.1% to 28.04%) in children with β thalassemia major over frequent blood transfusion [7 – 9].

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

Researcher performed the research at Mayo Hospital, Lahore from April to October 2017. The researcher enrolled one hundred and sixty-one patients of β thalassemia major for his research with three to twenty years of age and take as an average of not less than five blood transfusion (seventy-five ml packed cells /kg) per year and least twenty blood transfusion. Researcher expelled all those children from his research who are suffering from hemolytic anaemia instead of β thalassemia major. Researcher declared β thalassemia major to all those children who are suffering from serious microcytic hypochromic anaemia (haemoglobin is less than 5gm %) with decreased Hb of adults as well as fetal Hb is more than fifty percent of entire Hb while identification. Researcher gets a recommendation from organizational review panel along with written permission from the guardians of the children, conducted OGTT (oral glucose tolerance test) after

overnight fasting as well as the minimum passage of two weeks from the last transfusion. The glucose quantity for oral glucose tolerance test was 1.75g/kg till maximal 75 g diffused in water of 250ml. The researcher takes a blood specimen at zero and one hundred and twenty minutes after glucose management as well as dispatched to the laboratory with the objective of examining “B” and “C” hepatitis, serum ferritin, and plasma glucose. IGT: fasting plasma glucose less than 126mg/dl during two-hour plasma glucose is greater than or equal to 140mg/dl but less than 200mg/dl. Entire results with detailed information were recorded on Performa particularly made for said object. Researcher assessed the composed information by utilizing SPSS software and calculated percentage and periodicity of IGT, carried out categorization to manage consequences changer such as blood transfusion number, level of serum ferritin, age, and gender along with “B and C” hepatitis condition [16]. Researcher measured average as well as the standard deviation for patients’ age, height, weight and transfusion number.

RESULTS:

The researcher enrolled one hundred and sixty-one patients of β thalassemia major who are fulfilling the required criteria for research. Entire enrolled children having an average age of (10.55 + 4.90) years. The researcher also measured the average height and weight are presented as (132.8 + 16.34) cm and (41.5 + 10.78) kg respectively. The regularity of IGT was discovered in seventeen (10.56%) patients whereas one hundred and forty-four (89.44%) patients get clearance from IGT. Researcher performed categorization of IGT periodicity with the association to age. Among seventeen IGT children, the number of children having age between three to ten and eleven to twenty years was eleven (64.71%) and six (35.29%) children respectively. Researched also performed categorization of IGT regularity with the association to gender and hepatitis “B” and “C”. Among seventeen IGT cases, the number of male children was seven (41.18%) and female children was ten (58.82%) along with three (17.65%) hepatitis “B” and one (5.88%) had hepatitis “C” children respectively. Moreover, thirteen (76.47%) children were declared free from both kinds of hepatitis.

Table – I: Prevalence of Hepatitis

Hepatitis	Number	Percentage
HBV	3	17.65
HCV	1	5.88
No Hepatitis	13	76.47
Total	17	100

Table – II: Frequency of Impaired Glucose Tolerance, Age and Gender

Variables		Number	Percentage
Impaired Glucose Tolerance	Yes	17	10.56
	No	144	89.44
	Total	161	100
Age	3 to 10 Years	11	64.71
	11 to 20 Years	6	35.29
	Total	17	100
Gender	Male	7	41.18
	Female	10	58.82
	Total	17	100

DISCUSSION:

Entire children having β thalassemia major required frequent lifelong RBC transfusion for their protection. All β thalassemia major patients' faces a lot of issues in the case of transfusion inadequateness, meanwhile frequent blood transfusion is connected with bigger risk. Diabetics are the most significant challenge in β thalassemia major patients, therefore, twenty-five to fifty percent of these patients have impaired glucose tolerance test or diabetes [10, 11]. The number of children having age between three to ten year in eighty-six (53.42%) and eleven to twenty year was seventy-five (46.58%), measured average as well as standard deviation ($10.55 + 4.90$) years, the number of male and female was ninety-seven (60.25%) and sixty-four (39.75%) patients respectively as well as regularity of Impaired glucose tolerance was discovered in seventeen (10.56%) patients whereas one hundred and forty-four (89.44%) patients get clearance from IGT

The periodicity of impaired glucose tolerance alters from (7.1% to 28.04%) in children with β thalassemia major over frequent blood transfusion [7 – 9]. These results are in favours to our research. According to the research conducted by Chern JP et al presented the periodicity of impaired glucose tolerance as (8.5%) that is similar to our research findings [9]. Khalifa AS along with others determined that IGT is much frequent in children having β thalassemia major acquiring number of blood transfusion, that's might be subsidiary cause to developing as well as initial

loss of beta-cell mass, along with continuous insulin friction. Viral infection such as incurable hepatitis "C" might perform a role of in progression of IGT. Jaruratanasirikul along with associates in a researcher determined that the periodicity of impaired glucose tolerance in β -thalassemia major children acquiring hyper transfusion along with deficient iron chelating management was (12.5%) [13]. the clinical features of β -thalassemia major children who progress impaired glucose tolerance were wasting, a huge level of ferritin, stunting as well as lesser AUC insulin. The phenomena of IGT along with β thalassemia is continuously ambiguous, however, accounted primarily to insulin inadequacy due to iron deposition in the pancreas [14, 16]. And 2nd from insulin friction because of iron deposition in both liver as well as muscle [17]. The glucose mindedness as well as over diabetes might be the last outcome of constant insulin resistance, additional with developed decline level of circulating insulin [18].

CONCLUSION:

Researcher finalized that the regularity of IGT in children with β thalassemia major over frequent blood transfusion is too high, whereas several additional research on the same topic is mandatory for verification of our results.

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